

Development and validation of HPLC method for simultaneous determination of Hydrochlorothiazide and Alfuzosin

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Abstract : A simple and selective high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method was developed for the simultaneous determination of two anti-hypertensive drugs like Hydrochlorothiazide (HCT) and Alfuzosin (ALF). Separation was achieved using C18 column (4.6, 250 mm) with isocratic elution of the mobile phase composed of methanol and water with the ratio of 90 : 10 at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The optimized wavelength for the measurement of HCT and ALF is 260 nm. Quantification was based on measuring the peak areas. Two compounds were resolved with retention times of 1.7 and 2.5 min for HCT and ALF, respectively. Analytical performance of the proposed HPLC procedure was statistically validated with respect to linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, robustness, limit of detection and limit of quantification. The linearity ranges were 2–10 µg/mL for HCT and ALF with correlation coefficients >0.999. The developed method was found to be accurate, precise for simultaneous determination of HCT and ALF in tablets.

Keywords : Anti-hypertensive drug, Hydrochlorothiazide, Alfuzosin, HPLC chromatogram.

Introduction

Hydrochlorothiazide (HCT) (or 6-chloro-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,2,4-benzothiadiazine-7-sulfonamide-1,1-dioxide) is a moderately potent diuretic used in the treatment of hypertension either alone or with other antihypertensives¹. It is also used to treat edema associated with heart failure and with renal and hepatic disorders and the prevention of kidney stones. The United State of Pharmacopoeia (USP) describes an RP-HPLC method for the determination of HCT in tablets. Several analytical methods have been reported for the determination of HCT in pharmaceutical formulations includes polarography, LC, HPTLC and spectrofluorometry²⁻⁴.

Alfuzosin hydrochloride (ALF) is chemically designated as (*R,S*)-*N*-[3-[(4-amino-6,7-dimethoxy-2-quizolinyl)methylamino]propyl]tetrahydro-2-furan-carboxamide hydrochloride⁵. Alfuzosin belongs to a class of drugs called alpha-blockers. It is used to treat the signs and symptoms of benign enlargement of the prostate, by increasing the flow in urine which is reduced by benign prostatic hypertrophy^{6,7}. Literature survey reveals that methods have been reported for analysis of Alfuzosin hydrochloride by using RP-HPLC⁸.

A literature survey revealed that very few analytical methods have been reported for the determination of HCT and ALF. So in this present investigation, an attempt has been made to develop accurate, precise and economically viable reversed phase HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Hydrochlorothiazide and Alfuzosin in combined pharmaceutical tablets form. Fig. 1 shows the structures of HCT and ALF.

Fig. 1. The structures of Hydrochlorothiazide (HCT) and Alfuzosin (ALF).

Experimental

Materials :

Hydrochlorothiazide (99%) and Alfuzosin (98%) was supplied by Sigma Aldrich. HPLC-grade water, methanol and acetonitrile purchased by Sd.fine chem. Limited. Pharmaceutical tablets drugs of Hydrochlorothiazide and Alfuzosin was purchased from the local medical shop Vellore.

Preparation of standard solution :

A stock solution of Alfuzosin and Hydrochlorothiazide mixture was prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of drug in methanol to yield a final concentration of 1 mg/mL. This solution was further diluted with methanol to give a series of standards with concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of both drug. Preliminary studies showed that all analytes were stable in methanol.

Preparation of pharmaceutical tablets solution :

Hydrochlorothiazide tablets were weighed and finely powdered. HPLC-grade methanol was added to a quantity of the powdered tablets equivalent to 10 mg Hydrochlorothiazide, similarly 12.5 mg Alfuzosin was added in HPLC-grade methanol (into a 100-mL calibrated flask), and the solution was stirred for about 20 min then filtered through 0.4 micron filter.

Instrumentation :

The HPLC-system consisted of Waters series (Waters - 1525 Binary pump, and Waters 2487 Dual beam detector) connected to a computer loaded with empower software. A rheodyne manual injector with 20 μL loop was used. The column used was -C18 (4.6 \times 250 mm, 5 μm particle size-waters).

Results and discussion

Chromatographic conditions :

A mobile phase system consisting of methanol and water (90 : 10) v/v was used. The separation was achieved with the isocratic mode. The flow rate was 1.0 mL/min. The injection volume was 20 μL . The eluant was monitored by the diode array detector at 260 nm. The peak areas were plotted against the corresponding concentrations to construct the calibration graphs.

Analysis of pharmaceutical dosage form :

The optimized HPLC procedure can apply for the assay of this drug either single or combination in the pharmaceutical formulation (tablets). The tablets were prepared with the same solvent used for the preparation of the standard stock solutions (HPLC-grade methanol). The tablet eluted at their specific retention time. Recoveries were calculated using both standards. The assay results revealed satisfactory accuracy and precision as indicated from percent recovery and RSD% values (Table 1). It is evident from these results that the proposed method is applicable to the assay of this drug combination with a satisfactory level of accuracy and precision.

Linearity and concentration ranges :

The linearity of the proposed HPLC procedure was evaluated by analyzing a series of different concentrations for each of the two analytes. Table 1 represents the performance data and statistical parameters including linear regression equations, concentration ranges, correlation coefficients, standard deviations and regression analysis shows good linearity as indicated from the correlation coefficient values (> 0.999).

Fig. 2. HPLC chromatogram of Hydrochlorothiazide and Alfuzosin concentration ranges 2–10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Table 1. Linearity and precision data

Parameter	Hydrochlorothiazide	Alfuzosin
Linearity range (µg/mL)	2–10	2–10
Correlation coefficient	0.999	0.999
Precision <RSD (%)	0.8	0.9
Recovery (%)	98.80	98.70
LOD (µg/mL)	0.011	0.034
LOQ (µg/mL)	0.034	0.095

Detection and quantification limits :

According to the pharmacopoeial recommendations (United State Pharmacopoeia), the limit of detection is defined as the concentration that has a signal-to-noise ratio of 3 : 1, while for limit of quantification, the ratio considered is 10 : 1.

Precision and accuracy :

The within-day (intra-day) precision and accuracy for the proposed method were studied at 6 and 8 µg/mL concentration for Hydrochlorothiazide and Alfuzosin using three replicate. Similarly, the between-day (inter-day) precision and accuracy were tested by analyzing the same concentration for Hydrochlorothiazide and Alfuzosin using three replicate. The percentage relative standard deviation (RSD%) did not exceed 2.0%.

Robustness :

Robustness was examined by evaluating the influence of small variations in different conditions such as ratio of the mobile phase, working wavelength, flow rate (± 0.1 mL/min) and room temperature (± 3 °C). These variations did not have any significant effect on the measured

responses or the chromatographic resolution. RSD% for the measured peak areas using these variations did not exceed 3%.

Conclusion

In this study, a simple, specific and reliable isocratic elution HPLC procedure was developed for the assay determination of HCT and ALF in their pharmaceutical tablet form. To our present knowledge, no such specific and stability indicating procedure has been reported for the assay of these drugs. Finally, the method was thoroughly validated, therefore, it can be recommended for routine analysis and for checking quantitative studies either single or combination of ALF and HCT dosage form available in markets.

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